

EDUCATION OF CHILDREN IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM AND FRIENDSHIP OF PEOPLES IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. *The system of preschool education is the initial link in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main trend in the development of the educational process in modern conditions is the transition from education for the state to the education of self-awareness of the individual. At the same time, understanding by citizens of the strategy of political, socio-economic and spiritual development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is of particular importance.*

Keywords: *development in the spirit of patriotism, principles of learning stages, creativity, moral norms, creative ability, leading activity, development of the emotional sphere of children.*

An important part of the system of educational work is education patriotism and friendship of peoples. The great Russian philosopher and writer V.G. Belinsky in this regard noted that the upbringing of a moral personality is impossible without the formation of a sense of inseparable unity with one's country, love for it and civic responsibility. The significance and relevance of the problem of patriotic education has always been recognized by the people and has been the basis of a strong state. Inextricably linked with the idea of patriotic education in a multinational state is the formation of a culture of interethnic communication and the upbringing of children and youth in the spirit of friendship between peoples.

In the works of outstanding teachers K.D. Ushinsky, A.S. Makarenko, S.T. Shatsky's provisions on the social conditionality of the upbringing and development of the child's personality and the need for a rational organization of educational systems are traced. In the context of these provisions, the education of children and youth in the spirit of patriotism and friendship of peoples must have a rational methodological and methodological elaboration.

A significant contribution to the theory and practice of international patriotic education was made by the great teachers A.S. Makarenko, V.A. Sukhomlinsky, who noted the need to form a well-educated, conscious, active personality of a citizen with an understanding of civic duty and responsibility, courage, and a whole worldview.

In the early 90s of the twentieth century, the system of educational values changed dramatically. The educational process has moved from an educational paradigm to an educational concept, abandoning its educational function. The priority of the development of the cognitive sphere to the detriment of moral and spiritual development and the education of universal values contributed to the growth of various deviations in the youth environment, a decrease in positively directed civic activity, a drop in the level of tolerance, and a sharp increase in tension in interpersonal relations (N.D. Nikandrov). In modern conditions, there is a gradual reorientation of the consciousness of the psychological and pedagogical community towards understanding the problems of children and adolescents, the rejection of authoritarian models of education, the development of a new content of the state educational policy aimed at creating multivariate opportunities for children to participate in various types of upbringing and educational activities.

At present, the State Program of Preschool Education "First Step" links patriotic education with peace education, education in the spirit of friendship between peoples and the formation of tolerant consciousness in preschool children. Despite a certain elaboration of the problem in domestic national pedagogy in a certain period, in pedagogical science there is a crisis in the problematic field of studying the modern educational opportunities of the family. At the same time, it is in the family that the values of patriotism and friendship of peoples are formed and consolidated. Thus, the research problem is created by the contradiction between the demand for pedagogical theory and practice, the requirements of the state program and the low level of scientific and theoretical development of the topic. The search for ways of effective psychological and pedagogical support for the process of family education of patriotism and friendship of peoples with insufficient development of the problem in the special literature necessitates research. The purpose of the study is to identify the specifics of family education of patriotism and friendship of peoples in a multi-ethnic society and to develop a methodology for the psychological and pedagogical support of this process. The hypothesis of the study follows from the assumption that in the current social conditions of the transformation of social values, the family can become the most favorable environment for raising children in the spirit of patriotism and friendship of peoples if:

- educational work in the family will be based on the principles of science, integrity and consistency;

- the specificity of manifestations of patriotism and friendship of peoples among adult children in a multi-ethnic environment will be taken into account;

- family education in the spirit of patriotism and friendship of peoples will be based on the following mandatory areas: the study of the history of the Motherland;

- stories about the heroic past and outstanding personalities of the Motherland;

- reading folk tales, stories and stories about love for the Motherland;

- walks with children in historical places, excursions to the museums of the city;

- celebrations in the family of significant dates;

- conducting cognitive geographical games;

- studying the symbols of the state (flag, coat of arms, anthem);

- studying the history and culture of other peoples;

- participation of the family in cultural and mass holidays, weeks of friendship;

- in the presence of effective interaction between the family and the educational institutions in the education of patriotism and friendship of peoples.

The goal determined the following tasks:

1. Conduct a retrospective analysis of literary sources on the problem under study.

2. Reveal the specifics of family education of patriotism and friendship of peoples in modern conditions of the transformation of social and universal values.

3. Develop the content, methods and techniques of family education in the spirit of patriotism and friendship of peoples.

5. Develop methodological recommendations for psychological and pedagogical teams of educational institutions.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study are the ideas of A.N. Radishcheva, V.G. Belinsky, N.A. Dobrolyubov about the need to educate a person-citizen with high ideological and moral qualities, able to participate in social activities, striving for the improvement of the state,

for the freedom and happiness of the people; fundamental provisions of K.D. Ushinsky, A.S. Makarenko, ST. Shatsky on the social conditioning of the upbringing and development of the child's personality and on the rational organization of educational systems; ideas for updating the content of education in modern conditions N.D. Nikandrova, G.N. Filonova, D.M. Mallaev.

Research methods: retrospective analysis of literary sources, questioning method, testing and survey methods, content analysis method, methods of ascertaining, forming and control experiments, methods of primary and secondary mathematical processing. The scientific novelty of the study lies in the fact that the problem of family education of patriotism is subjected to theoretical and methodological analysis and friendship of peoples in modern conditions of transformation of social and universal values, the main methodological provisions regarding the specifics of raising a culture of interethnic communication and patriotic feelings in the family are clarified and concretized, a methodology has been developed for raising children in the spirit of patriotism and friendship of peoples by means of family education.

The theoretical significance of the study lies in the fact that the provisions of the theory of patriotic education are clarified and concretized, the specifics of family education in modern conditions are considered, the psychological and pedagogical patterns of patriotism and friendship of peoples in the family are revealed, the features of the manifestations of patriotic feelings and the culture of interethnic communication in children and their families are studied. parents, developed a methodology for family education of patriotism and friendship of peoples.

The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that, on the basis of the identified psychological and pedagogical patterns, a methodology for family education in the spirit of patriotism and friendship of peoples has been developed. A new direction of work of a teacher-psychologist and educator of a preschool educational institution is substantiated. And also the research materials can be used to improve the content and methods of education in schools and institutions aimed at working in the family, as well as in lecture courses for students of pedagogical universities and in the system of advanced training of teaching staff.

The following main provisions are considered:

1. Features of manifestations of patriotism and interethnic tolerance among children in a multinational society in modern Russian conditions of the transformation of social values.

2. The specifics of family education of patriotism and friendship of peoples in a multi-ethnic society, including: the study of the history of the Motherland; stories for children about the heroic past and outstanding personalities of the Motherland; reading folk tales, stories and stories about love for the motherland; walks with children in historical places, excursions to museums of the country; celebrating significant dates in the family; conducting cognitive historical and geographical games; the study of the symbols of the state (flag, coat of arms, anthem); the study of the history and culture of other peoples; family participation in cultural holidays, weeks of friendship.

3. Interaction between the family and the educational institution in the upbringing of children in the spirit of patriotism and friendship of peoples, involving the improvement of the qualifications of the psychological and pedagogical staff of educational institutions, the organization of parental general education on the problems of family education of patriotism and friendship of peoples, taking into account the age of students, monitoring and psychological and pedagogical diagnostics at all stages of educational work in educational institutions. The reliability of the study is determined by the level of theoretical and methodological analysis, the use of methods adequate to the hypothesis, the purpose and objectives of the study, the use of variation

statistics methods to assess the reliability of changes obtained during a series of formative experiments, the size of the experimental sample.

The modern educational process is characterized by variability and variability of the parameters of the educational space, sociocultural sources that affect the personality, which gives rise to the need for a flexible approach in educating the younger generation, creating conditions for the value-semantic choice of models of educational activity, taking into account all the factors affecting children and youth (N.G. Filonov, 2003). In this context, the ideas of K.D. Ushinsky about a person as a subject of education, about the rational organization of educational systems. In the works of K.D. Ushinsky, the methodology and experience of practical pedagogy are substantiated, the role of the social environment in the upbringing of the individual is deeply and comprehensively revealed. In the works of ST. Shatsky and A.S. Makarenko ideas K.D. Ushinsky found their continuation in the provision on the social conditionality of the upbringing and development of the child's personality.

The feeling of patriotism, expressed primarily in affection for one's native places, a small homeland, has been known since ancient times. With the development of the state, patriotism was filled with political meaning, associated with the demand for stamina and courage in wars, in defending the interests of the Fatherland, acquired a class content, where the interests of the class were more important than the interests of the Motherland.

In the new Uzbekistan, which is gradually entering the world democratic space, the concept of "patriotism" is defined as one of the forms of the dialectical combination of personal and public interests, the unity of man and society. The threat of nuclear self-destruction or ecological catastrophe required a rethinking of patriotism as a principle that commands everyone to contribute to their country's contribution to the preservation of the planet and the survival of mankind.

Consideration of the domestic concept of patriotic education is impossible without mentioning the works of A.N. Radishcheva, V.G. Belinsky, N.A. Dobrolyubov, who for the first time put forward the task of educating a person-citizen with high ideological and moral qualities, able to participate in social activities, striving for the improvement of the state, for the freedom and happiness of the people. A significant contribution to the theory and practice of civic education was made by A.S. Makarenko, V.A. Sukhomlinsky, who noted the need to form a well-educated, conscious, active personality of a citizen with an understanding of civic duty and responsibility, courage, a whole worldview, irreconcilable to shortcomings, laziness, indifference. In the works of Z.T. Hasanov developed the conceptual provisions of the theory and methodology of patriotism and friendship of peoples education, based on the pedagogical integration of knowledge of a number of sciences (philosophy, sociology, ethnology, linguistics, social and general psychology), analysis of domestic and foreign experience and representing a logically interdependent, integral system of knowledge. As D.M. Mallaev (2007), an important role in shaping the modern theory and practice of education of patriotism and friendship of peoples. Ethnocultural conditions have a significant impact on the socialization and upbringing of the individual (V.N. Gurov, 1989). In the process of upbringing, the national mentality of ethnic groups, which develops throughout the course of historical development, plays an important role. In this regard, the culture and traditions of the peoples of Uzbekistan since ancient times have a powerful peacemaking potential aimed at maintaining a fragile peace while distributing obviously insufficient resources in the region. We have divided these traditions into several categories:

- Traditions and customs applicable in relations between representatives of their nationality within the clan and village at the micro level;

- traditions and customs applicable in relations between representatives of their nationality at the macro level;

- traditions and customs applicable in the relationship between representatives of different nationalities within their own language group (for example, Tatar, Uighur, Turkic, etc.)

- traditions and customs applicable in relations between Uzbeks in general;

- traditions and customs applicable in relations between Uzbeks and people representing other regions. At the same time, these latter can be friendly neighbors.

This structuring of cultural peacemaking demands was caused by the need to build relationships and regulate

conflicts at various levels - from the level of one's family to the meta-level of human relations. This contributed to the development of a special mentality and self-identification as a representative of Uzbekistan and led to the fact that people of other nationalities within the region were perceived as “their own”, and, therefore, relations with them should be friendly. This led to the creation of national theaters, national editorial offices of magazines, national broadcasting in the languages of the peoples of Uzbekistan. By creating better conditions for representatives of several titular nationalities, the leadership of Uzbekistan, through its policy, to some extent contributed to the blurring of the boundaries between small ethnic groups. Today, the resurgent Republic needs a modern understanding and development of a new ideology of patriotism and friendship of peoples. And the main institution that directly affects the formation of these values in children is the family. The complexity and multifunctionality of the family determines an interdisciplinary approach to its study and interest in its problems from sociology, history, ethnography, demography, philosophy, social psychology, medicine, jurisprudence, Pedagogy. Since ancient times, various literary sources have noted the importance of solving family problems for society and the state. All holy books (the Bible, the Koran and others) reflect family traditions and customs of different peoples, give recommendations on creating and maintaining a family, and emphasize its social value. Family relations were studied by Plato, Aristotle, F. Bacon, M. Montaigne, J.J. Rousseau, I. Kant, G. Hegel and many other consuming philosophers. The increase in changes in family lifestyle since the beginning of the twentieth century has led to the actualization of scientific interest in this area of research.

The system of socialization in the family, according to T. Parsons, guarantees the emergence of generations that are more and more adapted to society. Without the influence of family education, it is impossible to imagine the process of a child's socialization, and its underestimation, according to many researchers, leads to distortions in public education and pedagogical voluntarism, an exaggeration of the role of the school in the process of educating a personality. Darmodekhin formed the scientific foundations of the value approach to the family, theoretical provisions based on the awareness of the socio-cultural value of the family, and served as the foundation for the axiological approach to this issue within the framework of philosophy, cultural studies and anthropology, and pedagogy. Although the educational function is recognized as the most important function of the family, the educational potential of families is very different and depends on a number of factors: family type, structure, material security, social status, traditional ways of education, religious affiliation, region of residence, level of culture, education and pedagogical competence of parents, as well as a number of other factors. The role of the family in the education of patriotism has been repeatedly emphasized in many works. In studying family opportunities for education in the spirit of patriotism and friendship among peoples, one cannot refuse to use experience from the history of pedagogy, despite its clear and ideological orientation.

Researchers such as P.M. Rogachev and M.A. Sverdlin, A.I. Kholmogorov, Kh.N. Abdurakhimova, N.N. Bulanova, I.V. Kogevin and R.G. Kukharchuk, V.I. Chekalin, developed methods of family education in the context of patriotism and internationalism. It should be noted that the problem of education of patriotism and friendship of peoples in the family is insufficiently illuminated in modern pedagogy. In the articles by R.V. Radzhabova, O.A. Smetanina, N.F. Velikhanova points out the need for interaction between the family and educational institutions in the formation of patriotic feelings, citizenship and tolerance. The necessity of coordinating the requirements of teachers and parents, personal example, optimization of the social microenvironment, taking into account the multiculturalism and multiethnicity of the region where the family lives are noted. In the study of A.K. Nisskaya (2008) concludes that children's emotional perception of the Motherland correlates more with the position of their parents than with special learning conditions in an educational institution. An analysis of the specifics of upbringing in the Dagestan family showed that its feature is a frequent interethnic character. In nationally mixed families, there is a real mutual influence of the cultures of both parents. The specificity of the Uzbek family remains a high percentage of intergenerational ties. This contributes to the reproduction and preservation of traditions, but hinders the penetration of innovations, preserving in a peculiar way the mentality of the peoples living in Uzbekistan. Another feature of the Duzbek family is its frequent large families. According to scientists, a large family has a much greater potential in cultivating a culture of interethnic communication and friendship between peoples in comparison with other types of families, since these families, due to their special mentality, are more adapted to the assimilation of universal human values. The existing special space of the multinational microenvironment creates favorable conditions, mediated by kinship, for interethnic socialization. Folk traditions and cultural values of a multi-ethnic environment are an important factor in the formation of an individual and a citizen, and, consequently, in the education of a patriot and an internationalist.

Despite the centuries-old positive experience of Uzbeks in the formation of a culture of interethnic communication and the education of patriotism, it should be noted that in the modern century, in the course of a series of transformations, transformations and reforms, a significant number of factors have arisen that contribute to the positive development of interethnic relations. The modern Uzbek family does not exist outside the influence of these factors. It acts as the main institution for understanding what is happening in society, and the upbringing of children is a kind of indicator of the reaction of society to the ongoing changes. An analysis of literary sources led to the conclusion that it is now necessary to develop methods for raising children in the spirit of patriotism and friendship of peoples, including by means of family education.

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